

Workplace experiences of language teachers with ADHD

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14789398>

Corresponding author: Ms. **Gretchen Clark**, Language Education Center, Ritsumeikan University, 2-150 Iwakura-cho, Ibaraki, Osaka, 567-8570, Japan

Email: gclark@fc.ritsumeai.ac.jp

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-1993-6604>

Gretchen Clark holds an MA in TEFL/TESL from the University of Birmingham. She currently teaches English in the Faculty of Business Administration at Ritsumeikan University, Osaka, Japan. She is an active member of the Japan Association for Language Teaching's Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion Committee and she believes in creating professional spaces for people to share their lived experiences, grow and support one another.

Mr. **Marc Jones**, Toyo University, Faculty of Global and Regional Studies, Department of Global Innovation Studies, 5-28-20 Hakusan, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo, 112-8606, Japan

Email: jones056@toyo.jp

ORCID: <https://www.orcid.org/0000-0002-2004-1809>

Marc Jones is a lecturer in the Department of Global Innovation Studies at Toyo University, Japan and a PhD candidate at TU Dortmund, Germany. He has worked in many English Language Teaching contexts in Japan. His main research interests are listening and phonology, duoethnography, and ADHD in language teachers.

Workplace experiences of language teachers with ADHD

While childhood Attention-Deficit/ Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) has been extensively researched in recent years, studies concerning how adults with ADHD cope in their private lives or in the workplace are relatively few in number. The current study used a questionnaire survey to investigate the experiences of language teachers (N=48) with ADHD in the workplace. A content analysis of the textual responses to open-ended items showed that language teachers experience issues related to focus and self-control, task steps and process, task initiation and execution, memory, and emotional and physical responses. Three additional themes include: workplace relationships, coping mechanisms, and unique skills due to their ADHD. Findings indicate that the work life realities of teachers intersect with their work with students so much more research is needed to investigate how these unique relationships affect students' learning.

Keywords: ADHD; language teaching; disability studies; content analysis

Introduction

Attention-Deficit/ Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is a mental condition that is usually detected as a child. Bergey and Filipe (2018), report that 5% of children and 7.2% of adolescents around the world are affected. Hundreds of thousands of studies concerning children with ADHD have been published leading to implementations of vast support systems for children within family life or at school in the US (Barkley & Benton, 2022).

However while ADHD is often detected during childhood, symptoms may persist into adulthood in varying degrees (Barkley & Benton, 2022; Hallowell & Ratey, 2021). Barkley and Benton (2022) postulate that “*ADHD is real. And it’s not a condition that affects only kids*” (p. 2; emphasis in original). Yet in the United States, where the prevalence of ADHD diagnosis is highest, only 4% of adults have been diagnosed. Barkley and Benton (2022) attribute this to several factors including: ADHD wasn’t widely recognized as a disorder prior to the 1980s and during that time there was a popular misconception that ADHD is a myth and that any behavioral trouble can be rectified using coping methods. Nevertheless, many adults today are becoming aware of issues and

seeking treatment in order to improve the quality of their lives. Much research is still needed to fully support adults with ADHD.

This paper reports on a qualitative study of the work experiences of language teachers with ADHD and how their experience may affect their teaching practice. We begin the paper with an overview of the condition, how it may affect work and relationships, and a summary of the limited research concerning language teachers with ADHD. This section concludes with a statement of our research questions. The following section describes the participants and details about the construction of the questionnaire. We describe the coding methods used for a content analysis of the textual responses and relate the measures we used to improve accuracy of our interpretations. We conclude the paper with a discussion of the results in relation to existing research and note limitations of the study.

Literature review

Overview of ADHD

The *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders* (5th ed.; DSM-5; American Psychiatric Association, 2013) describes ADHD as: the “persistent” pattern(s) of inattention and/or hyperactivity-impulsivity affecting the quality of two or more life-settings such as in daily life, school or at work (Barkley & Benton, 2022, pp. 269-271). ADHD is a neurological condition in which the hormone, dopamine, is not deployed readily in order for an individual to react to a stimulus and perform. Specific symptoms are related to executive dysfunction such as trouble with memory, organization, and prioritizing. These are displayed in a myriad of potentially problematic ways from physical symptoms such as inattention, hyperactivity, unbounding energy, or talkativeness to those that are difficult to detect such as racing thoughts or spacing out. An additional 91 symptoms often seen among adults with ADHD are outlined in Barkley and Benton (2022, pp. 271-276).

Adult ADHD in the workplace

In the workplace, ADHD adversely affects adult employees as individuals and the teams they work with. At the individual level, a person with ADHD might struggle in several areas including efficient work execution and one-on-one relationships (Fuermaier et al., 2021). Illness associated with stress or burnout completing daily work tasks (Brattberg, 2006) and the fallout from the possible stigma (Mueller et al., 2012) should one disclose their condition to the company may also occur. Working within teams might prove to be difficult if the individual has problems with time management and completion of tasks (Fuermaier et al., 2021; Hilton et al., 2009). These weaknesses might hamper smooth working relationships with colleagues in general (Adamou, 2013). ADHD may prevent people from building a solid career trajectory and thus seniority and financial benefits are never realized (Doshi et al., 2012).

Having ADHD can be an asset at work, however, as found by a few small scale studies. White and Shah (2006) found that people with ADHD excel in creative pursuits and are able to problem-solve. People who have ADHD are suited to entrepreneurial careers in which impetuosity fuels risk-taking and autonomy are important (Verheul et al., 2016). The propensity to hyperfocus in one area of interest contributes to high levels of expertise (Baer, 2015). This tendency also surfaces across disciplines, often allowing a person with ADHD situations in which their ability to synthesize knowledge in fresh ways is useful (Baer, 2015).

Neurodivergence in education

Research on childhood ADHD and neurodiversity is prevalent, with many studies and volumes focusing on effects of the condition on academic achievement and ways to support students. Barkley and Benton's (2022) and Halloway and Ratey's (2021) two most recent books on ADHD explore ADHD across the lifespan. Studies by Hechtman et al. (2016) and DuPaul et al. (2021) measured long term effects of ADHD on university success and later adult work performance.

Sedgwick (2018) conducted a review of 74 publications reporting research done with university students with ADHD. The meta-analysis suggests that students with ADHD experience problems in coping with workloads and self regulation, yet may also be talented. Although it is difficult to generalize from a meta-analysis of students toward a population of teaching professionals, it appears that the challenges and successes may plausibly apply across these adult populations.

According to Bergey and Filipe (2018), increasing numbers of studies are being conducted with adults. A few focus on educators with disabilities in higher education. Bolt and Penketh (2016) edited an entire volume dedicated to how the ableist narrative promoted by the academy is outdated and should be challenged. Dolan (2023) reports on a case study of tertiary level academics who suffer silently with invisible impairments, including ADHD. Wood and Happé's (2023) work relates the experiences of autistic educators in the UK. Brown et al. (2018) suggest ways academic professional development organizations can support educators with disabilities. In the field of language teaching, two duoethnographic papers address neurodivergence among teachers: Cuervo-Rodríguez and Castañeda-Trujillo's (2021) personal account of working with dyslexia and Jones and Noble (2023) on ADHD are important contributions and serve as an impetus for the research reported in this paper.

Research Questions

This paper reports the qualitative data obtained from a Google Forms survey in which the following research questions were explored:

- 1) How does ADHD affect the execution of work tasks for language teachers?
- 2) How does ADHD affect relationships in their work environment?

Methods

Researcher positionality statement

We are members of the ADHD language-teaching community whose voices we hope to amplify with the findings of this paper. This positionality allows us access to the greater ADHD population and also enables us to analyze the collected data against our own experiences living and working with ADHD. In our survey of the literature on the working environments of neurodiverse people in general, as well as those with ADHD, we found little information about what our contemporaries deal with at their workplaces. Building on the duoethnography of Jones and Noble (2023), we desire to continue the momentum of awareness-raising with a view to making our workplaces more inclusive and supportive of those with ADHD. We believe that while there are areas in which we may struggle, there are plenty in which we contribute positively with our expertise, inspiring colleagues and acting as role models for the people we teach. To this end, we designed the current study to canvas the greater ELT population worldwide and find out more about their realities at work and how they navigate professional relationships with the diverse people they work with. In the words of David Bolt (2015), in the academy, it is through “the very diversity of minds and bodies that we are ultimately unified” (p. 11) and our world is better for it. With this in mind, we aim to provide an emic yet objective examination of the self-reported experiences and feelings of the ADHD language teaching community.

Participants

As reported in Jones and Clark (in press), participants were recruited by convenience and snowball sampling between December 2022 and February 2023. Of 57 participants who passed the screening criteria of having an official diagnosis or a self-diagnosis of ADHD, 48 provided qualitative answers to the questionnaire.

More participants were self-diagnosed (n=26) than diagnosed by a medical professional (n=22). Regarding gender, 31 participants identified as female, 14 as male, and three as non-binary, of which one identified as non-binary/female. The vast majority of participants were based in Japan (n=37), with 2 based in other Asian countries, 6 in Europe, 2 in the USA, and 1 in Africa,. The mean age was 43.5 years old, with a range from 27 to 70 years old. Most participants worked in university (29), although six worked in elementary schools, seven in junior high schools, six in high schools, eight in private language schools, and eight in other settings. Several participants worked in more than one setting.

Questionnaire

Questionnaire development

A questionnaire was constructed to answer the above research questions as part of a comprehensive study. To ensure internal consistency and ease of comprehension for participants, a pilot questionnaire was first constructed and sent to colleagues who were not part of the target sample. This was to ensure that anybody becoming part of our intended snowball sample would not be over-familiar with the final instrument and answer automatically without considering the questions. The pilot questionnaire consisted of 11 sections, though some questions were only available depending on how participants answered prerequisite items. See the Appendix for the complete instrument.

Following feedback from colleagues trialing the questionnaire, changes were made resulting in the final version of the instrument (see Appendix). These changes were related to presentation of questions in a tabulated section in the form instead of in isolated subsections, and changing the scale of the self-efficacy items from 0-10 to 0-5, making the questionnaire less confusing.

This article focuses on thematic analysis of only the qualitative question items due to the scope and space available to a journal article. Quantitative analysis may be found in Jones and Clark (forthcoming).

Sampling and sharing

The questionnaire was shared by the authors on social media (Mastodon, LinkedIn, Facebook) and by email, with contacts advised to share the questionnaire with their contacts. This method of eliciting participants resulted in a sample with features of convenience sampling and snowball sampling.

Content analysis

As the goal of this study was to investigate the experiences of language teachers with ADHD, the research falls under the social-constructivist paradigm in which the coding process involved “look(ing) for the complexity of views rather than narrowing meanings into a few categories or ideas” (Creswell & Creswell, 2018, p.8). As such, data were coded using a content analysis method in which not only major themes but also latent nuances were identified and subsequently quantified to understand general perspectives across the entirety of the participant pool.

The coding process was iterative, with the first author using the qualitative data analysis program, NVivo for Mac (QSR, 2018) to construct the preliminary codebook for the project. During an initial pass through the data, it was determined through *Eclectic Coding* (Saldaña, 2016) that issues of executive dysfunction as described by Barkley and Benton (2022) were mentioned by all participants. This provided a partial framework for subsequent examinations of the data set. At this stage, *In Vivo Coding* was useful to identify specific language that was repeated by a number of participants which was then applied to similar concepts in the remainder of the data using *Concept*

Coding, an analytic coding method which harnesses “the *ideas* [emphasis in original] suggested by the study” (Saldaña, 2016, p.120). Once the codebook was finalized, the second author hardcoded the entirety of the data independently. After the first round of coding, the codes generated by both researchers were compared and interrater reliability was calculated to be 80.62%. In subsequent video conferencing meetings, discrepancies were negotiated to form 100% agreement. The results are presented in the findings section of the paper.

Findings

Of the 57 participants, 48 expanded on their answers to the 5 point-scale portion of the questionnaire. A thematic analysis revealed eight main themes. Five were related to the types of executive dysfunction Barkley and Benton (2022) describe. These are issues related to: focus and self-control, task steps and process, task initiation and execution, memory, and emotional and physical responses. Three additional themes were identified. The first was related to workplace relationships, the second was related to coping mechanisms and the final theme was concerning unique skills the respondents identified in themselves due to their ADHD.

Theme 1: Focus and self-control

Difficulty with maintaining focus was a main theme that was identified with 29 of the 48 respondents (60.41%) indicating some struggle with distraction especially while teaching.

Participant 22 remarked that they “get distracted easily during the lessons: sometimes we start doing an activity and end up doing something completely different.” Participant 21 echoed this sentiment explaining, “Because of my distraction, I’m more likely to jump around in the lesson, change my mind as I’m explaining”. Inconsistency was also mentioned by four participants, one of whom attributed this to a “compulsion to improvise” (P38). Two respondents (P18 and P27) mentioned that questions from students about grammar caused their lessons to “get stuck in the weeds” (P27).

Three respondents remarked that they had trouble focusing on students when they spoke, and in fact, interrupted students more than usual when ideas occurred to them. Outside of the classroom, some participants lamented a loss of focus on correcting student work or completing long-term projects such as writing research papers. One participant (P32) said inability to focus contributed to unfinished tasks and said, “I sometimes switch things mid-task and so I will not realize something is not actually done”.

In addition to distraction, 23 (47.92%) respondents reported problems with conceptualizing time or experiencing “time-blindness”. Participants mentioned they “lose track of time” (e.g., P14), or that it’s “an issue” (P41). One participant said they were “awful” at time management (P32). Lesson pacing is a theme that emerged with one participant saying, “my pacing is always interesting. I’m keenly aware of how long students have been doing something and I try never to let them get bored” (P36). Lessons that are fast-paced are “engaging” (P22). This suggests that time is a major factor in teachers’ work, yet this is not reported by all participants.

Despite these challenges, 16 (33.33%) participants mentioned their keen ability to hyperfocus on tasks. In the classroom, an example of hyperfocusing is a teacher who shares a topic that they find interesting with students which results in students also becoming excited (P29). Another participant acknowledges the negative side of hyperfocusing when delivering input: “I can overwhelm learners easily, rather than dripfeed info as needed” (P55). For many participants, this ability surfaces during the planning stages. One participant (P1) wrote “I really like to find accurate data, images, and real-life examples for my classes, and this leads to hyperfocusing on the prep stage”, but the same participant alluded to the downside of this as it can contribute to overpreparation and increased busyness. Another participant (P50) acknowledged the negative side of hyperfocusing on work and lamented that it leaves little personal time which has led to a nervous breakdown in the past. Concerning administrative work, some participants found deadlines helped them hyperfocus on the task to finish. One participant (P32) explained, “I can also hyperfocus if I

really have to get some things done, and sometimes I can do a lot or a very good job on something in a short amount of time.” Another participant (P8) said, “I get these productive cycles where I am able to concentrate and work at certain times of the year.”

Theme 2: Teaching materials and lesson organization

A second theme concerning problems with organizing physical teaching materials as well as the teaching process was identified. Two salient sub-themes emerged: Twenty-nine participants (60.42%) mentioned problems with organization and 30 participants (62.50%) wrote about issues with completing processes. In terms of organization, several participants mentioned the collection and management of materials to be an essential part of their teaching process. Participant 2 elaborated: “In terms of organization, I keep every file and every piece of paper, and I keep everything related to teaching highly organised, but everything else is chaos.” This high attention to systematizing materials often doesn’t transfer to the participants’ workspaces with both Participant 32 and Participant 41 lamenting their workspaces as “messy”.

Once in the classroom, several respondents described ‘scattered’ lesson plans (P5, P27) in which activity steps don’t flow in a logical manner. Several participants pointed out that giving instructions proved to be a struggle. Participant 2 explains,

I do think I cause problems for students by leaping from A to Z. I have to really talk myself through a task in advance to make sure that my instructions are clear, and if I'm not careful, the instructions and warm-up can take over from the main activity.

This sentiment was echoed by Participant 29 and Participant 48. This disorganization might also occur during the execution of a task, with Participant 29 counteracting any diversions by keeping to

a strict time schedule and “not[ing] what things I can cut if necessary if I happen to run over, or go off on a tangent.”

Inadequate planning for teaching was also a strong theme. The word “scattered” was used by Participant 5 to describe their planning and work process. Even when provided with or using a set lesson plan, two participants reported having trouble following the steps (P9 and 10). Two participants lamented that trouble planning contributed to negative feelings such as anxiety (P37) and stress (P30). Poor planning is not always a negative experience for some. For example, Participant 22 doesn’t rely on prior-planning at all but instead completes preparation in the minutes before a lesson begins. They describe their experience as a positive one and explain,

I can say that I am a good teacher: students tell me every day, current and previous employers have always praised my performance etc. However, I do not plan my lessons. At all. Ten minutes before the lesson I start panicking, decide the activities I'm going to use and find material (P22).

Theme 3: Task initiation and execution

The (in)ability to begin and complete tasks was also mentioned frequently. Nineteen participants (39.58%) reported problems with procrastination and an inability to start a task. Uninteresting and tedious tasks, especially related to administrative duties such as paperwork or student assessment were mentioned most frequently. Participant 4 described their experience, saying “I am terrible about grading and giving written feedback. Every semester I tell myself I will stay on top of it better this semester. And every semester I am scrambling to finish grading at the end of the semester.” Complicated tasks proved to be a problem for Participant 60, who said, “I avoid doing activities involving lots of organisation because I get confused.” For P24, perfectionism contributed to their inability to begin planning lessons. Difficulty starting tasks carried over into other areas of work

such as professional development with Participant 8 writing, “I sometimes cannot bring myself to conduct research or submit proposals [to publications or conferences].”

Just as tasks are sometimes difficult for participants to begin, they are also difficult to complete. Twelve people (25.00%) mentioned having trouble following through with a task. “It’s so hard to get stuff done on time. Deadlines are stressful, even if it’s for routine work, which I ultimately enjoy, like planning the next lesson” (P47). Participants mentioned working through the night up until deadlines (P26), or as in the case of Participant 42 fail to follow through altogether due to waning of motivation when nearing the end of completion of a task.

Transitioning between tasks was also mentioned by 3 respondents (6.25%). Two (P34, P40) believe multitasking or doing tasks in “parallel” as P34 describes, helps them complete tasks quickly and efficiently while Participant 40 has difficulty switching from one to another. They explain, “My ADHD slows me down during transitions in my lesson because switching tasks within the lesson can take a minute to “buffer” in my brain, and I have trouble filling that space.”

Theme 4: Memory

Regarding memory, we found many respondents (20, 41.67%) mentioned problems remembering materials or steps in a process. Forgetfulness sometimes surfaced on the microlevel with participants forgetting a myriad of things including physical objects or materials needed for lessons (e.g., work bag, computer cords) or intangible things such as deadlines, timetable changes, and passwords. While teaching, memory is an issue for some. Participant 38 wrote, “I cannot be consistent with rules, schedules about quiz [sic] or assignments. I forget or just come up with new ideas randomly.” This was echoed by Participant 10, who explained,

I struggle with memory and inattention. I sometimes feel as though I am forced to approach every lesson plan and class with a "blank slate" because I cannot access or process information in either the past or the present moment.

Similarly, three participants (6.25%) had trouble accessing short-term memory to complete detailed work and were frustrated by errors even after proofreading.

Theme 5: Emotional and physical responses

Within this theme, it was found that many respondents felt that having ADHD contributed to emotional responses regarding their work. Some respondents reported a general binary feeling of simply feeling “on” (P1, P37) or “off” (P37) but most explained how ADHD might affect their emotional status in detail. More than half, twenty-eight (58.33%) participants commented on negative feelings with anxiety, stress, overwhelm, self-consciousness being mentioned frequently. Some participants mentioned an extreme workload as being a contributing factor to task avoidance or a complete shut down. Indeed, Participant 8 remarked, “I feel overwhelmed most of the time and the anxiety I feel can be almost too crippling at times.” Participant 50 was an extreme case who mentioned a possibility of a “nervous breakdown”. These feelings were also directed inward with several respondents reporting low self-image. Participant 32 explained, “Honestly, [ADHD is] really affecting my motivation, my sense of community, my confidence, and my mental health.” Participant 51 described their long-term feeling, and stated “Feeling ‘damaged’ has been something I have had to deal with my whole life. It has not been pleasant.” It is unclear from the data if these emotions are expressed outwardly but two mentioned hiding or “masking” their true feelings (P1, P10). Participant 29 explains their experience:

Sometimes there is a brain fog that I just can't push through some days, and it makes it a struggle to keep myself focused, much less my students. A teacher mask helps with most of these issues, but having to adapt last minute on those days and try to keep the kids engaged, and then feeling like I haven't taught them anything because I could only give them busy work, is hard to push past.

On the other hand, 22 participants (45.83%) reported having positive feelings toward their work, especially with regard to their life in the classroom such as having high energy, enthusiasm, motivation, and curiosity. Participant 38 wrote, "I am kind, considerate, fun, energetic, lively and carefree." Participant 12 wrote, "I think I am very motivated and motivating." These positive feelings make their work life enjoyable according to several participants (P19, P36, P50).

Theme 6: Workplace relationships

Within this theme, two sub-themes emerged, one regarding relationships with students (36, 75.00%) and a second regarding relationships with colleagues (29, 60.42%). Concerning students, several participants mentioned meeting student needs in general as an important pillar of their teaching approach (e.g., P7, P22). Respondents expressed compassion and sympathy for students of low ability and regularly differentiated materials or methods to help them. One explained, "I have an eye for pitfalls in which students might get lost due to unclear goals within an activity, and I try to build activities that every student feels they can at least partially succeed at." (P10). For some, their flexible teaching approach came about as a reaction to their own weaknesses currently (P21, P49) or as a child (P7, P42). Participant 8 is transparent about their own mental health struggles and believes it is an asset to forming positive relationships with students. They explained, "I also feel that because I am open about my depression and ADHD, the students feel more at ease with me and they also share their stories with me, in a way I feel they trust me more (P8). Participant 42 believes

their teaching style evolved due to negative past experiences as a student. They explained, “Having had negative experiences as a child due to issues with my undiagnosed ADHD, it drives me to be understanding and more patient with my students who struggle” (P42).

While in general participants deemed having ADHD to be an asset when engaging with students, responses were mixed regarding colleagues. Participants mentioned having diverse interests as being a way to forge relationships with colleagues (e.g., P14, P17). For example, Participant 30 wrote they can “I have thousands of ideas per minute and can infect others with passion.” However, on the other hand, some respondents felt having ADHD was a handicap in some interpersonal situations. Two participants reported engaging in public disagreements with colleagues (P1, P18) while some (P12, P19) reported a general feeling of awkwardness or an inability to form strong relationships with others in the workplace. Two reported that they avoid their colleagues altogether (P37, P49).

Theme 7: Coping strategies

Twenty-three (47.92%) described coping mechanisms they use to counteract any trouble brought on by ADHD symptoms. Using strategies, making systems, task-switching, and overplanning were the top four strategies mentioned. Most frequently, respondents reported using some kind of strategy but did not elaborate. However, some specific strategies used include using bullet journals to manage tasks (P55), posting announcements on the institution learning management system to remind themselves and students of what was covered in a lesson (P21) and reusing past lesson plans and materials (P23). Several participants have developed systems to manage workflow. For example, Participant 24 reported making lesson plan templates to streamline the planning process. A third coping strategy was also identified: task-switching. Some participants reported purposefully alternating between tasks to maintain motivation and interest both for themselves and their students

(e.g., P29, P34). Finally, overplanning was often used to quell anxiety throughout the semester, both before classes commence and in the midst of the term.

Theme 8: Unique skills

Finally, there was a strong theme of pride regarding unique tasks these respondents felt they excelled at or executed better than their neurotypical colleagues (30, 62.50%). Creativity was mentioned by the majority of participants. For Participant 40, creativity is expressed in this way: they can “create lesson plans that are eye-catching and easy to follow. My ADHD also helps with spontaneous inspiration, which aids me during lesson activities.” Participant 25 reported an affinity for materials gathering and creation which they report “brings richness to my classes!” Participant 23 echoes this sentiment and explained they are able to generate variations for a given activity very easily. A second sub-theme that emerged was a keen ability to solve problems and improve existing materials or systems. For example, P21 said “I can quickly think of innovative ways to solve problems and don’t feel shy to share them”. In addition, several participants felt they had a high propensity for detail-oriented work. Participant 29 explained, “I always write down the time schedule for the day or lesson, and also note what things I can cut if necessary if I happen to run over, or go off on a tangent”. Participant 40 reported they notice and keep track of details concerning students’ personalities and language learning progress. Finally, a few participants described an innate ability to synthesize information in a unique way. For example, Participant 2 believes they can analyze a situation from a variety of perspectives. They also believe they can “integrate materials into an overarching system”. Both Participant 5 and Participant 7 believe they make connections between ideas that other people do not.

Discussion

At work, the participants in this study struggled with various aspects of executive dysfunction, such as trouble with *focus and self control, materials and organization, task initiation and execution, memory*, and trouble regulating *emotional responses*, especially those of a negative variety that affect the daily tasks of lesson planning, delivery, and out-of-class marking and administrative work. These findings align with the symptoms mentioned in the DSM-5 (2013) and the work of Barkley and Benton (2022) and others.

Difficulties with maintaining positive social relationships was prevalent in our sample just as Fuermaier et al. (2021) found in their study. However, this difficulty was limited to relationships with colleagues rather than with students. In contrast, interactions with students were framed positively and prioritized, with great effort dedicated to cultivating supportive learning environments for all students, especially those who may have learning differences and manage ADHD.

Participants mentioned various coping strategies they use to mitigate any disruptive effects of ADHD. This is to be expected as by adulthood it can be surmised that a person with ADHD has had repeated opportunities to exercise and hone personalized responses to situations in which disruptive symptoms occur. However, when reflecting on their work, many participants alluded to extreme levels of preparation for lessons. In some cases, these efforts affected their mental and physical well being, resulting in overwork or mental breakdowns. While burnout (Brattberg, 2006) was not mentioned specifically it would not be surprising if some participants reached this state. In contrast, at the same time, there was a strong theme of pride in which divergent thinking was mentioned as a unique skill. Like White and Shah (2006), most participants believed their ADHD made them more creative. Some noted their ability to offer alternative perspectives, and problem-solve while adjusting lesson plans to student needs or time limitations.

Overall, the study provides a detailed account of how ADHD affects the working lives of a population of 48 language teachers. The data shows that at least for the teachers in this sample, ADHD affects the work process in both negative and positive ways but most individuals employ mechanisms to cope. The participants are conscientious in their work and seek to provide the best possible outcomes for their students. Studies such as this one are important in raising awareness about ADHD. We hope it provides insight into the experiences of neurodiverse faculty and leads to positive organizational change in which all faculty, especially those who have ADHD, are supported in their professional endeavors.

Limitations

There are several limitations that make our findings ungeneralizable to the larger ADHD language educator population. First, our participant pool was limited by the shallow reach of convenience and snowball sampling methods. The survey was posted on various social media platforms but garnered only those who are connected to us online. This fact most probably also contributed to the fact that most of the teachers who responded work at the tertiary level just as we do. Finally, given the nature of qualitative data analysis, the findings are based on our interpretations. While we aimed to represent the data accurately in the way the participants reported, and cross-check our evaluations, other researchers could conceivably come to different conclusions with the same data.

Notes on contributions

Both authors contributed to the writing of the article and the conceptualization of the study.

Gretchen Clark led the qualitative analysis and Marc Jones assisted.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to express our gratitude to all of the participants for their time and effort, and without whom the project would not have been possible. We would also like to thank Carolyn Blume, Jules Bündgens-Kosten, Robert J. Lowe, and Adam Littleton for feedback on earlier drafts of this article.

Disclosure statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

References

Adamou, M., Arif, M., Asherson, P., Aw, T.-C., Bolea, B., Coghill, D., Guðjónsson, G., Halmøy, A.,

Hodgkins, P., Müller, U., Pitts, M., Trakoli, A., Williams, N., & Young, S. (2013).

Occupational issues of adults with ADHD. *BMC Psychiatry*, *13*(1), 59.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-244X-13-59>

American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders*

(5th ed). <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.books.9780890425596>

- Barkley, R. A. & Benton, C. (2022). *Taking charge of adult ADHD: Proven strategies to succeed at work, at home, and in relationships*. The Guilford Press.
- Baer, J. (2015). The importance of domain-specific expertise in creativity. *Roeper Review*, 37, 165-178. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02783193.2015.1047480>
- Bergey, M. & Filipe, A. (2018). ADHD in global context: An introduction. In M. Bergey, A. Filipe, P. Conrad, & I. Singh (Eds.), *Global perspectives on ADHD: Social dimensions of diagnosis and treatment in sixteen countries* (pp.1-8). Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Bolt, D. (2015). The importance of disability research. *Revista de La Facultad de Medicina*, 63(3Sup), 11–12. <https://doi.org/10.15446/revfacmed.v63n3sup.52718>
- Bolt, D., & Penketh, C. (Eds.). (2016). *Disability, avoidance, and the academy: Challenging resistance*. Routledge.
- Brattberg, G. (2006). PTSD and ADHD: Underlying factors in many cases of burnout. *Stress and Health*, 22, 305–313. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smi.1112>
- Brown, N., Thompson, P., & Leigh, J. (2018). Making academia more accessible. *Journal of Perspectives in Applied Academic Practice*, 6(2). 82-90.
<https://doi.org/10.14297/jpaap.v6i2.348>
- Creswell, J. & Creswell, J.D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Cuervo-Rodríguez, K. A. & Castañeda-Trujillo, J. E. (2021). Dyslexic individuals' narratives on their process of becoming English language teachers. *HOW*, 28(2), 79-96.
<https://doi.org/10.19183/how.28.2.621>

- Dolan, V. L. B. (2023). "...but if you tell anyone, I'll deny we ever met": The experiences of academics with invisible disabilities in the neoliberal university. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 36(4), 689–706.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09518398.2021.1885075>
- Doshi, J. A., Hodgkins, P., Kahle, J., Sikirica, V., Cangelosi, M. J., Setyawan, J., Erder, M. H., & Neumann, P. J. (2012). Economic impact of childhood and adult attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder in the United States. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 51(10), 990-1002.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaac.2012.07.008>
- DuPaul, G., Gormley, M., Anastopoulos, A., Weyandt, L., Labban, J., Sass, A., Busch, C., Franklin, M., & Postler, K. (2021). Academic Trajectories of College Students with and without ADHD: Predictors of Four-Year Outcomes. *Journal of Clinical Child & Adolescent Psychology*, 828-843. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15374416.2020.1867990>
- Fuermaier, A. B. M., Tucha, L., Butzbach, M., Weisbrod, M., Aschenbrenner, S., & Tucha, O. (2021). ADHD at the workplace: ADHD symptoms, diagnostic status, and work-related functioning. *Journal of Neural Transmission*, 128(7), 1021–1031.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00702-021-02309-z>
- Hallowell, E. M., & Ratey, J. J. (2021). *ADHD 2.0: New science and essential strategies for thriving with distraction--from childhood through adulthood*. Ballantine Books.
- Hechtman, L., Swanson, J. M., Sibley, M. H., Stehli, A., Owens, E. B., Mitchell, J. T., Arnold, L. E., Molina, B. S. G., Hinshaw, S. P., Jensen, P. S., Abikoff, H. B., Perez Algorta, G., Howard, A. L., Hoza, B., Etcovitch, J., Houssais, S., Lakes, K. D., Nichols, J. Q., Vitiello, B., ... Stern, K. (2016). Functional adult outcomes 16 years after childhood diagnosis of

attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder: MTA results. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 55(11), 945-952. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaac.2016.07.774>

Hilton, M. F., Scuffham, P. A., Sheridan, J., Cleary, C. M., Vecchio, N., & Whiteford, H. A. (2009). The association between mental disorders and productivity in treated and untreated employees. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 51(9), 996-1003. <https://doi.org/10.1097/JOM.0b013e3181b2ea30>

Jones, M., & Clark, G. (2024). Language teachers with ADHD: Self-efficacy and framings. *Fremdsprachen Lehren und Lernen*, 53(2). <https://doi.org/10.24053/FLuL-2024-0025>

Jones, M., & Noble, M. (2023). "What about teachers?": A duoethnographic exploration of ADHD in ELT. *Explorations in Teacher Development*, 29(1), 34-45. <https://td.jalt.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/ETD-291-Jones-Noble.pdf>

Mueller, A. K., Fuermaier, A. B. M., Koerts, J., & Tucha, L. (2012). Stigma in attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. *ADHD Attention Deficit and Hyperactivity Disorders*, 4, 101–114. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12402-012-0085-3>

QSR. (2018). *N-Vivo for Mac (12.7.0)* [Computer software].

Saldaña, J. (2016). *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers* (3rd ed.). Sage Publications.

Sedgwick, J. A. (2018). University students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD): A literature review. *Irish Journal of Psychological Medicine*, 35(3), 221–235. <https://doi.org/10.1017/ipm.2017.20>

Verheul, I., Rietdijk, W., Block, J., Franken, I., Larsson, H., & Thurik, R. (2016). The association between attention-deficit/hyperactivity (ADHD) symptoms and self-employment. *European Journal of Epidemiology*, 31(8), 793–801. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10654-016-0159-1>

White, H. & Shah, P. (2006). Uninhibited imaginations: Creativity in adults with Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 40, 1121-1131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2005.11.007>

Wood, R., & Happé, F. (2023). What are the views and experiences of autistic teachers? Findings from an online survey in the UK. *Disability & Society*, 38(1), 47–72. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2021.1916888>

Appendix: Final questionnaire

We (Marc Jones and Gretchen Clark) would like to ask for your help answering the following questionnaire "ADHD in Language Teachers". This is not a test so there are no "right" or "wrong" answers and you don't have to provide personally identifying information. Please answer honestly, as only this will guarantee the success of the investigation. Thank you very much for your help.

Please note: if you are using a phone to answer the questionnaire you may need to scroll right to see all answer options.

Purpose of the study

This questionnaire is part of a research study exploring the experiences of language teachers with Attention-Deficit/ Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). You will be asked questions about if and when you have had a formal diagnosis, and how ADHD affects your teaching practice and professional relationships. The final section of the questionnaire asks you to evaluate your self-efficacy with

regard to your workplace tasks. Demographic questions will also be asked. In total, the questionnaire will take 15-20 minutes to complete.

Who is eligible to participate?

In order to participate in this study you must currently be a language teacher.

Do I have to take part?

Your participation is voluntary and you are free to withdraw at any time, without prejudice. It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you withdraw before submitting the questionnaire, none of your answers will be recorded. You may withdraw by closing your browser window.

Privacy and Confidentiality

The answers you provide in this questionnaire are anonymous and you will not be identified. Your personal data will not be collected, unless you choose to sit for an interview with one of the researchers. The final item of the questionnaire asks you if you would be willing to do so and you will be asked to enter your name and your email address. The data collected with this questionnaire will be stored in a password protected computer. No email addresses are captured unless volunteered. We strongly recommend, for privacy concerns, that you do not answer this questionnaire while logged in to a work-based Google account. Some employers may monitor staff communications.

If you have any questions or concerns, please contact Marc Jones: jones056@toyo.ac.jp

Do you have or suspect you have ADHD?

As of 1st January 2023, how old are you?

What is your gender?

In which country were you raised?

In which country do you live/work?

What is your teaching context?

How are you employed?

How well do you speak the main language(s) of the country you live in?

How literate are you in the main language(s) of the country you live in?

Have you had a formal diagnosis of ADHD?

In which country were you diagnosed with ADHD?

When were you diagnosed? (Approximate year)

What was your experience of diagnosis like?

How long have you known or suspected you might have ADHD? (Approximately)

Please rate the following statements according to your belief.

ADHD affects my planning for classes.

ADHD affects the activities I intend to use.

ADHD affects the materials (web, apps, documents, devices, realia) I intend to use.

If you have anything further to add about lesson preparation, please leave a comment.

Please rate the following statements according to your belief.

ADHD affects how I deliver teacher input, such as vocabulary or grammar instruction.

ADHD affects how I give task instructions.

ADHD affects how I provide feedback to students

ADHD affects how I facilitate student-to-student interaction.

ADHD affects how I facilitate review of previous teaching.

ADHD affects how I motivate students.

ADHD affects how I keep students focused on tasks.

ADHD affects the pacing of my lessons.

ADHD affects how I use visual tools such as slides and/or whiteboards.]

ADHD affects my use of reminders such as pop-up notifications or timers.

ADHD affects how I assess learning during class (feedback, taking notes on performance).

ADHD affects my assessment of learning outside of class (for example, marking, feedback, submitting grades).

If you have anything further to add about teaching, instruction, and/or assessment please leave a comment.

Please choose the value that best reflects your belief.

ADHD affects my relationships with colleagues.

ADHD affects my relationships with students.

In this part, please indicate the degree to which you disclose your ADHD at work.

Do you tell your students you (suspect you) have ADHD? Yes/No

Do you tell your colleagues you (suspect you) have ADHD? Yes/No

Do you tell your employers you (suspect you) have ADHD? Yes/No

Choose the value that best matches your beliefs about your abilities in general.

Express my views freely on language teaching matters.

Get the instructional materials and equipment I need.

Keep students on task.

Increase students' memory of what they have been taught in previous lessons.

Motivate students who show low interest in lesson activities.

Get students to work well together.

Create a welcoming classroom environment.

Increase students' motivation to attend lessons.

Help students to trust me as their teacher.

Help students to believe they can achieve success in language learning.

How does ADHD contribute positively to your teaching?

How does ADHD contribute negatively to your teaching?

How does ADHD contribute positively to your work life?

How does ADHD contribute negatively to your work life?

Please write any other comments about your ADHD and how it affects your teaching life both in and outside the classroom.

Finally, would you consider participating in a follow-up interview on Zoom with either researcher, Marc Jones or Gretchen Clark? If so, indicate who you prefer and please provide your name and email address here so we can contact you to arrange a time. Thank you for taking time to complete our questionnaire.